

Photocatalysed Reactions of Benzyl Alcohol on Zinc Oxide*

E. P. YESODHARAN, V. RAMAKRISHNAN and J. C. KURIACOSE

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras 600 036

Manuscript received 24 April 1978, revised 30 September 1978, accepted 24 April 1979

The photocatalysed oxidation of benzyl alcohol on zinc oxide has been investigated. Benzaldehyde, toluene and hydrogen peroxide are formed as the products. Their reaction in the dark is negligible. The influence of different parameters like method of preparation of the catalyst, irradiation time, solvent effect etc was studied. Detailed investigations reveal that the products result from the reaction of radicals in the liquid phase as well as a direct surface reaction. Considering the various types of oxygen species on ZnO under these conditions it is possible that oxygen either in the form of the molecule itself or in the form of a molecular anion is the entity responsible for the reaction. Though the products remained the same in solvents of different polarity their quantities as well as their behaviour is different in different solvents. Thus, more than the nature of the organic substrate itself it is the conditions to which it is subjected that determines the nature as well as the distribution of products.

NUMEROUS studies have been made on the interaction of organic substrates and oxygen in the presence of ZnO. Information concerning the interaction of oxygen with the excited state of ZnO is available from ESR investigations as well as photochemical studies¹⁻⁵. The photooxidation of isopropyl alcohol in presence of ZnO and oxygen has been studied in some detail^{1,6}, the products being identified as acetone and hydrogen peroxide. This photocatalytic effect of ZnO has been explained by Schwab⁷ on the basis of its n-type semiconductivity. The formation of hydrogen peroxide involves the removal of electrons from ZnO, acceptor sites being created simultaneously where the alcohol gets dehydrogenated. Illumination will increase the population of electrons in the conduction band. Preliminary studies have shown that, provided there is continuous access of oxygen to the surface, benzyl alcohol undergoes dehydrogenation on ZnO illuminated with radiation of wavelength 3650 Å. The present studies were undertaken to elucidate the role of oxygen as well as the function of ZnO itself in the photocatalytic reactions of benzyl alcohol.

Experimental

The light source used in all the experiments is a Hanovia-high pressure quartz mercury arc. Radiations above 3800 Å are not absorbed by ZnO as is revealed by its reflectance spectrum. The lamp is mounted horizontally above a mechanical shaker and provided with an aluminium foil shade to reflect the light downwards. The reaction vessel consists of a pyrex tube with an opening for introducing the solids and liquids and a small side tube for bubbling gases. This is provided with an outer jacket through which water at the desired temperature can be circulated. 0.35 gm of the catalyst and 30 ml of the liquid under investigation are taken in the reaction vessel which is then closed and clamped to the platform of the mechanical shaker and shaken throughout the experiments. Samples are removed from the tube at intervals and analysed.

Almost all types of commercially available ZnO samples were found equally active as photocatalysts. Other oxide samples were prepared from Zn(NO₃)₂, Zn(OH)₂, ZnC₂O₄ and ZnCO₃ by well known standard procedures⁸. For the experiments conducted in the absence of oxygen, nitrogen free from oxygen was bubbled for about half an hour, after which the gas stream was shut off, the reactor closed and irradiated. During the withdrawal of samples nitrogen was turned on again. It was observed that the rate of shaking did not affect the rate of reaction as long as the sample was kept in suspension.

The estimation of hydrogen peroxide was done by iodometry^{9,10}. Benzaldehyde and toluene were determined by gas chromatography.

The benzyl alcohol was purified by Martin's procedure¹¹ and the solvents by standard methods. They were all found to be spectroscopically pure.

Results

The products of the photocatalysed reaction of benzyl alcohol are hydrogen peroxide, toluene and benzaldehyde. The product yield increases with increase in weight of the catalyst to reach a steady value. This may be because with increase in the quantity of the catalyst, the amount of light absorbed also increases until enough ZnO is present to spread completely and uniformly in the reaction vessel to absorb the maximum amount of light. Further addition of ZnO may increase only the depth of ZnO and since light does not reach the interior of the catalyst bulk, it is not effective. This is further confirmed by the observation that the bigger the reaction vessel, the higher this limiting amount of catalyst.

Reactions were carried out in solvents of different polarity viz. cyclohexane (dielectric constant=2.05),

* Presented at the National Symposium on Catalysis held at I.I.T., Kharagpur, Dec. 29-31, 1975.

acetonitrile (dielectric constant=38.8) and water (dielectric constant=80).

Cyclohexane :

Figs. 1, 2 and 3 show the effect of concentration of the alcohol in cyclohexane on the formation of benzaldehyde, toluene and hydrogen peroxide respectively at 28°. The yield of aldehyde and toluene steadily increases with time of irradiation. But in the case of hydrogen peroxide at lower concentrations of the alcohol the amount reaches a maximum, then decreases, again goes to the same maximum and then decreases as the reaction time is increased.

Fig. 1. Influence of concentration of benzyl alcohol on the formation of benzaldehyde

Fig. 2. Influence of concentration of benzyl alcohol on the formation of toluene

Fig. 3. Influence of concentration of benzyl alcohol on the formation of H₂O₂.

Acetonitrile :

The nature of the curves for the formation of aldehyde in acetonitrile is similar to that in cyclohexane except that the reaction is much faster in acetonitrile (fig. 4). Even though the amount of hydrogen peroxide formed also is larger than in cyclohexane, the amount formed does not pass through maxima and minima as in cyclohexane. Interestingly, no toluene could be detected here.

Fig. 4. Influence of concentration of benzyl alcohol on the formation of benzaldehyde

Water

Though the dielectric constant of water is much higher than that of acetonitrile, the amount of all the three products were found to be less in water. The yield of toluene is found to pass through a maximum with time of irradiation (fig. 5). This is understandable since toluene itself when irradiated in water with ZnO was found to give hydrogen peroxide. The relative rate of formation of peroxide as well as the rate of decomposition of toluene in these solvents is given in fig. 6.

Fig. 5. Influence of the concentration of benzyl alcohol on the formation of toluene

Fig. 6. Formation of hydrogen peroxide in the presence of toluene in different solvents

The effect of products on the reaction was studied in all the solvents. Thus benzaldehyde and toluene initially added to the reaction mixture do not have any

effect on the rate while initially added hydrogen peroxide decomposes readily in water reaching a minimum concentration and then increasing slowly without influencing the rate of formation of other products (fig. 7). For obvious reasons experiments with initially

Fig. 7. Influence of initially added hydrogen peroxide on the formation of benzaldehyde and toluene from benzyl alcohol

added hydrogen peroxide could not be studied in other solvents. This effect of hydrogen peroxide shows that benzaldehyde is not formed through a secondary reaction with the hydrogen peroxide. The decrease in the amount of hydrogen peroxide with time in cyclohexane is not due to any interaction by either the aldehyde or the toluene. At higher concentrations of the alcohol, the amount of aldehyde increases much more rapidly than the hydrogen peroxide. But at lower concentrations, they are formed in more or less equal amounts.

A few experiments were carried out in a nitrogen atmosphere with ZnO suspended in solutions of benzyl alcohol in these solvents. After four hours of irradiation, the amount of the aldehyde and hydrogen peroxide formed were negligibly small.

Discussion

Neither the alcohol nor the solvent absorb the incident radiation. Zinc oxide is the only entity absorbing the incident radiation. Thus the oxidation succeeds the light absorption by zinc oxide. It is now necessary to delineate the process by which the excited zinc oxide sensitizes the oxidation of benzyl alcohol and also identify the active state of oxygen responsible for the above oxidation. It has been established by previous workers^{3,12,13} that in other similar systems the formation of hydrogen peroxide on irradiated zinc

oxide surfaces involves the preliminary reaction of adsorbed molecular oxygen. Light absorption by ZnO (a semiconductor) results in the excitation of the valence band electron to conduction band. The electron trapped in the conduction band is captured by the adsorbed oxygen. This process results in the formation of O_2^- .

Since a specie like O^- can be formed even in the dark^{1,4,13-15} on zinc oxide the fact no oxidation occurs in the dark rules out the involvement of O^- .

The C-H bond of the adsorbed benzyl alcohol can interact with the positive hole and can lead to the production of a radical of the following type.

These radicals can react with oxygen as follows.

In polar media the splitting of benzyl alcohol will be followed by the capture of O_2^- and the initial and final products are shown below.

The essential features of the mechanism are :

i) the mechanism of the reactions occurring in a polar medium is slightly different from the mechanism in non-polar media.

ii) Hydrogen peroxide and photooxidation yield should be greater in polar media than in nonpolar media unless other complications such as solvent participation in the reaction occur.

iii) Products could be due to surface reactions as well as reactions of the radicals desorbed into the solution.

In the present investigation the solvents studied are cyclohexane, acetonitrile and water. The reactivities cannot be explained by polarity alone. The interesting observation was that the nature of the products formed depended upon the solvent. In all these solvent media benzaldehyde and H_2O_2 are formed. But in water and cyclohexane toluene is also formed. It is also seen from fig. 8 that photodecomposition of hydrogen peroxide is suppressed in alcohol-water combination. Water and alcohol molecules are expected to compete in occupying adsorption sites on oxide. As such a competition has been established in the case of rutile as the catalyst¹⁶. But acetonitrile molecules are not expected to compete with alcohol molecules in occupying the adsorption sites. This explains why despite the high dielectric constant of water the yields of products are not high.

Fig. 8. Decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in pure water and 0.1M solution of benzyl alcohol in water

Rabinowitch¹⁷ established that water adsorbed on zinc oxide can be split by 3650 Å radiation and the photosplitting leads to the production of H and OH. Capture of an electron by water leading to the formation of H_2O^- (step 10) has been shown to be a feasible process^{18,19}.

Further reactions of OH radicals are as follows :

Step 14 explains the dissociation of H₂O₂. Irradiated suspensions of zinc oxide in cyclohexane containing oxygen can yield cyclohexyl radical and hydrogen. Thus in the case of water and cyclohexane H[•] formation is envisaged. When adsorbed benzyl alcohol is split two types of bond breaking can occur. The most usual breaking mode is the rupture of C-H bond and the consequent formation of C₆H₅CHOH radical. On the other hand in cyclohexane and water the presence of H_(ads) can cause splitting of OH bond also.

This leads to the production of the benzyl radical. OH breakage could be specific for this molecule as the resonance stabilisation of the benzyl radical (the product) could be the driving force of the reaction. Further reactions can be as follows :

The reaction of benzyl radical with H[•] can account for the formation of toluene. The selective formation of toluene in cyclohexane and water are thus explained.

When the amount of benzaldehyde becomes sufficiently large oxidation by oxygen to benzoic acid occurs at a detectable rate. Thus when benzaldehyde is actually added to the system before irradiation the

yield of the aldehyde and peroxide show a downward trend whereas the yield of toluene, a slowly oxidisable material remains unaffected (fig. 9). This may be

Fig. 9. Influence of initially added benzaldehyde on the formation of toluene and hydrogen peroxide from benzyl alcohol

Fig. 10. Rate of formation and disappearance of toluene

explained as follows. The formation of benzoic acid may result in rapid decomposition of H₂O₂. The acid assists the decomposition of H₂O₂. The aldehyde can consume oxygen or H₂O₂ for the oxidation reaction. As a result of these steps the yield of aldehyde and hydrogen peroxide will decrease while the yield of toluene remains the same. But toluene itself undergoes

a slow reaction to yield hydrogen peroxide. In water the rate of formation of toluene decreases with time whereas its disappearance rate shows an increase with time (fig. 10). Thus the yield of toluene shows a maximum at a point where the rate of formation is equal to its disappearance rate, (fig. 9). In cyclohexane the yield of H_2O_2 shows an oscillation with the time of irradiation (fig. 3). When the concentrations of benzyl alcohol is large this effect is absent. As already discussed hydrogen peroxide is formed in certain steps (7 and 9) and disappears in some other steps (12, 13, 14) and the maxima may occur when the rate of formation equals the rate of disappearance. The involvement of cyclohexane as a reactant is indicated. Further work is needed to clarify this point.

Acknowledgement

Grateful acknowledgement is made to N. S. F. for financial support.

References

1. J. C. KURIAKOSE and M. C. MARKHAM, *J. Catalysis*, 1962, 1, 498.
2. Y. FUJITA and T. KWAN, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1958, 31, 379.
3. T. R. RUBIN, J. G. CALVERT G. T. RANKIN and W. MACNEVIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2850.
4. M. C. MARKHAM, M. C. HANNAN, R. M. PETER NOSTRO and C. B. ROSE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 5394.
5. T. I. BARRY and F. S. STONE, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1960, 335A, 124.
6. I. KOMURO, Y. FUJITA and T. KWAN, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1959, 32, 884.
7. G. M. SCHWAB, *Adv. in Catalysis*, 1957, 9, 229.
8. M. RAVINDRAM, *Chemical Age of India*, 1971, 22, 63.
9. C. N. CHARI and M. QUERESHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 97.
10. M. C. MARKHAM and K. J. LAIDLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1953, 57, 363.
11. A. R. MARTIN and C. M. GEORGE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1413.
12. V. A. GARTEN and K. EPPINGER, *Solar Energy*, 1961, 5, 77.
13. J. C. KURIAKOSE and M. C. MARKHAM, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 2232.
14. M. C. MARKHAM, J. C. KURIAKOSE, J. DEMARCO and C. GIAQUINTO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 932.
15. R. J. KOKES, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 99.
16. R. I. BICKLEY and R. K. M. JAYANTY, 'Photoeffects in adsorbed species', Faraday Discussion of the Chemical Society, 1974, B. 14.
17. E. RABINOWITCH, 'Photosynthesis I', Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, NY. 1945, p. 73.
18. J. L. MAGGE and M. BURTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 523.
19. F. S. DANTON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1948, 52, 490.